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CULTURAL PLURALITY AND ITS ROLE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the theme of cultural plurality in Physical Education classes, using the National Curriculum Parameters and the National Common Curriculum Base as primary sources, aiming to identify the guidelines of the PCN and BNCC for Basic Education in Physical Education classes. The methodology used was a literature review, and the results obtained through the theoretical and bibliographic survey elucidate some of the major current challenges in implementing public education policies directed at Physical Education. The application of cross-cutting themes and content blocks, both from the National Curriculum Parameters and the National Common Curriculum Base, still presents difficulties in practice, making it necessary to increase the approach to these themes in order to improve the pedagogical practice of Physical Education teachers.

Keywords: Cultural plurality. School Physical Education. National Curriculum Parameters (PCN). National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC).